

THERMO ELASTIC-PLASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS OF CERAMIC-METAL GRADED MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The thermo elastic-plastic behavior of ceramic-metal functionally graded materials (FGMs) was investigated in this paper. The inelastic properties were first evaluated using micro mechanical approaches: the rule of mixture, mean-field micro mechanics(MFM) and self-consistent micro mechanics(SCM), then an elastic-plastic finite element model was used to calculate the thermal stress in the material. The results show that:(1) the response given by the MFM and SCM is nearly same but the response given by the rule of mixture is different; (2) the thermo elastic-plastic behavior exerts significant influences on the thermal stress relaxation characteristics of the FGMs.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic-metal functionally graded materials (FGMs) are a new type of composite material developed in the late 1980s. This material is characterized by the continuous transition or ladder transition of the constituent, micro structure and properties. The FGM has drawn great attention from all over the world for its superior material properties and its new design ideas [1,2]. Because of the great difference between metal and ceramic in mechanics and thermal expansion properties, when a powder metallurgy is used to synthesize ceramic-metal FGMs, high thermal stress is generated inside the material, which leads to plastic deformation produced in the pure metal layer, ceramic particles reinforced matrix graded layers and ceramic-metal network graded layers, and so non-elastic behavior is presented. We have observed that the property of graded layers has a significant influence upon the thermal stress relaxation, resistance to thermal shock and thermal fatigue of FGMs, and the proper control of the non-elastic behavior of the graded layers may obviously improve the material mechanical properties in high temperature condition. However, great difficulties exist in nonlinear thermal analysis and design of FGMs, which is related to nonlinear micro mechanics and macro thermal elastic-plastic stress analysis. So far, most contemporary researches on FGMs concentrate on the linear analysis and design. Nonlinear investigation has just begun in the world. The study of thermo elastic-plastic properties of FGMs is very limited [3,4]. Consequently, the investigation on thermo elastic-plastic behavior in the synthesis process of FGMs shows important practical significance and theoretical value to synthesize good quality ceramic-metal FGMs in the design and fabrication.

MODEL FOR THE THERMAL STRESS ANALYSIS

In this paper, a disk-shaped ceramic-metal FGM plate is considered. The plate is 6mm in thickness, 30mm in diameter, and has 11 graded layers. The top pure metal layer is 1mm in thickness, the rest layers, including the bottom pure ceramic layer, are all 0.5mm in thickness. The calculation condition for the thermal load is sintered at 1300°C and cooled down to room temperature(25°C). The compositional distribution in the FGM interlayers is described by $c=(x/d)^p$, where c is the ceramic volume fraction, x is the distance measured from the metal side, d is the plate thickness, and p is the compositional distribution exponent that controls the shape of the distribution function. Due to the axisymmetric problem, the axisymmetric finite element formula is employed. The cylindrical coordinate is chosen to be used and the Z -axis is taken along the thickness of the plate. Nonlinear finite element method is used to analyze thermo elastic-plastic stress of FGMs. The thermo elastic-plastic stress-strain relationship in layers is described as:

In elastic region:

$$\Delta\{\sigma\} = [D]^i (\Delta\{\varepsilon\} - \Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T) \tag{1}$$

In plastic region:

$$\Delta\{\sigma\} = [D]_{ep}^i (\Delta\{\varepsilon\} - \Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T) \tag{2}$$

where $[D]^i, [D]_{ep}^i$ are macro elastic and elastic-plastic stiffness matrix in the i th layer, $\Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T$ is the increment of thermal strain produced by temperature, $\Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T = \{\alpha\}^i \Delta T, \{\alpha\}^i$ is thermal expansion coefficient matrix in the i th layer. The effective node load is expressed as:

In elastic region :

$$\Delta T^e = \int [B]^T [D]^i \Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T dV \tag{3}$$

where $[B]$ is the strain matrix of the element.

In plastic region:

$$\Delta T^e = \int [B]^T [D]_{ep}^i \Delta\{\varepsilon\}_T dV \tag{4}$$

The governing equation is expressed by

$$[K] \Delta\{\delta\} = \Delta\{T\} \tag{5}$$

where $[K]$ is the tangential stiffness matrix of the structure.

MICRO MECHANICAL PREDICATION OF THE ELASTIC-PLASTIC PROPERTY

In order to calculate the thermal stress of the FGM, based on the micro structure characteristic in graded layers, the effective properties should be calculated by micro mechanical approaches firstly. Because of the continuous transition in the micro geometry, from a dispersive structure to a network structure and from the network structure to an alternative dispersive structure, the calculated results of FGM thermal stress depend not only on the properties of the graded layers but also on the micro mechanical approaches; different predicting approaches may lead to different calculating results. There are three micro mechanical approaches which have been widely used for predicting the effective properties of FGMs: the rule of mixture, mean-field micro mechanics (MFM) and self-consistent micro mechanics (SCM). For comparison, they are briefly outlined below. Since our main attention is concentrated on the elastic-plastic properties, therefore we only give the formulas of the elastic-plastic stress-strain relationship.

THE RULE OF MIXTURE

This approach describes the effective elastic-plastic stress-strain relationship as [5]

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_1(1-c) + \sigma_2 c \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon_1(1-c) + \varepsilon_2 c \quad (7)$$

$$q = \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_1}{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1} \quad (8)$$

where σ_1 , ε_1 and σ_2 , ε_2 are the corresponding true stress and strain of the metal and ceramic, respectively, and σ_c and ε_c are the composite flow stress and strain, q is the slope of a correspondence line on the stress-strain curve.

THE MEAN-FIELD MICRO MECHANICS

Recently, Weng and his colleagues [6] developed a micro mechanical approach to deal with the elastic-plastic properties of particle-reinforced composite. According to this approach, the effective secant bulk and shear moduli of FGMs can be determined by

$$\frac{k^{**}}{k_1} = 1 + \frac{c(k_2 - k_1)}{(1-c)\alpha_1^s(k_2 - k_1) + k_1} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\mu^{**}}{\mu_1^s} = 1 + \frac{c(\mu_2 - \mu_1^s)}{(1-c)\beta_1^s(\mu_2 - \mu_1^s) + \mu_1^s} \quad (10)$$

where k^{**} and μ^{**} are the effective secant bulk and shear moduli, k_1 , μ_1^s and k_2 , μ_2 are the corresponding secant bulk and shear moduli of the metal and ceramic phases.

THE SELF-CONSISTENT MICRO MECHANICS

The elastic-plastic self-consistent micro mechanics was recently developed by Nan et al [7]. In term of this approach, the effective secant bulk and shear moduli of the FGMs can be calculated by

$$(1-c)\frac{k_1 - k^{*s}}{3k + 4\mu^{*s}} + c\frac{k_2 - k^{*s}}{3k_2 + 4\mu^{*s}} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$(1-c)\frac{\mu_1 - \mu^{*s}}{\mu_1 + y^{*s}} + c\frac{\mu_2 - \mu^{*s}}{\mu_2 + y^{*s}} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where } y^* = \frac{\mu^{*s}(9k^{*s} + 8\mu^{*s})}{6(k^{*s} + 2\mu^{*s})}.$$

ANALYZING RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The above approaches have separately been used by the authors for different FGMs systems. In this paper, to evaluate the effectiveness of these methods, they are simultaneously used for predicting the effective properties of a same FGM system of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Ni}$. The pure ceramic and metal properties are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for } \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, & \quad E=380.0\text{GPa}, \quad \mu=0.25, \quad \alpha=5.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}, \\ \text{for } \text{Ni}, & \quad E=205.0\text{GPa}, \quad \mu=0.31, \quad \alpha=13.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}, \\ & \quad \sigma_y = 150.0\text{MPa}, \quad H=669.0\text{MPa} \end{aligned}$$

where σ_y and H are the initial yield stress and the linear strain hardening parameter. The effective properties of a same FGM system of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Ni}$ predicted by the three different micro mechanical approaches are indicated in figures 1-2.

Figure 1 indicates the distribution of the linear hardening parameter along the FGM thickness estimated by the three approaches. From this figure, the three approaches predict the different hardening parameter distributions. Figure 2 shows the initial yield stress distribution along the FGM thickness. From this figure, the result predicted by the MFM is close to that by the SCM, but the result by the rule of mixture is obviously different. The maximum difference between the result by the MFM and that by the rule of mixture is 9.07%.

Based on the effective properties in the layers of the FGM calculated by the three micro mechanical approaches, Figure 3-5 show the relationship between the maximum radial stress, axial stress and shear stress and the distribution exponent p in the elastic-plastic cases. In the figures, for different distribution exponent p , the MFM and SCM give nearly the same elastic-plastic thermal stress and optimum compositional distribution, but the results given by the rule of mixture are quite different.

Figure 6 displays the comparison between the maximum radial stress, axial stress and shear stress and the distribution exponent p in the elastic and elastic-plastic cases, in which the effective properties in layers of FGM are calculated by the mean-field micro mechanics (MFM). From

figure 6 it is seen that the elastic-plastic thermal stresses are much lower than the elastic thermal stresses .

CONCLUSIONS

Through the thermo elastic-plastic stress analysis of a concrete Al_2O_3/Ni FGM, two conclusions can be drawn as follows:

(1) The results of the elastic thermal stress and the elastic-plastic thermal stress of FGM determined by the MFM and SCM is about the same; Simultaneously, the optimum compositional profile of FGM determined by the maximum stress given by the MFM and the SCM is also the same;

(2) For different distribution exponent, the elastic-plastic thermal stress is much lower than the elastic thermal stress; that is to say, the thermo elastic-plastic behavior exerts significant influences on the thermal stress relaxation characteristics of the FGMs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the National Science Foundation under the Grant 59302017.

REFERENCES

1. M. Yamanouchi, M. Koizumi and T. Hirai (editors), Proc.1st Int. Conf. on FGM,1990,Sendai, Japan.
2. J. B. Holt, Z. A. Munir (editors), Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. on FGM, Nov.1-4,1992,San Francisco, California.
3. R.L.Williamson and B.H.Rabin, Numerical Modeling of Residual Stress In Ni- Al_2O_3 Graded Materials, Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. on FGM, San Francisco California, 1992, Nov.1-4,55-65.
4. M.J.Pindera and T.O.Williams, Thermoplastic response of metal-matrix composites with homogenized and functionally graded interfaces, Composites Engineering, 1994, Vol.4, No.1,129-145.
5. J.T. Drake, R. L. Williamson , B. H. Rabin , Finite element analysis of thermal residual stresses at graded ceramic-metal interfaces: Part II. interface optimization for residual stress Reduction ,J.Appl. Phys.1993,73 (3):1321-1326.
6. G.P.Tandon and G.J.Weng, A theory of particle-reinforced plasticity, ASME Journal of Applied Mechanics, Vol.55, No.3, 126-135,1988.
7. C. W. Nan, R. Z. Yuan, and Q. J. Zhang , The elastoplastic behavior of metal/ceramic functionally graded materials , Proceeding of FGM'92, 91-98, 1992, San Francisco, U.S.A..

Figure 1 Linear hardening parameter distribution predicted by the three micro mechanical approaches ($p=1.0$)

Figure 2 Initial yield stress distribution along the FGM thickness predicted by the three micro mechanical approaches ($p=1.0$)

Figure 3 The relationship between the maximum elastic-plastic radial stress S_{xx} and distribution exponent p

Figure 4 The relationship between the maximum elastic-plastic axial S_{yy} stress and distribution exponent p

Figure 5 The relationship between the maximum elastic-plastic shear stress S_{xy} and distribution exponent p

Figure 6 Comparison between the maximum elastic and elastic-plastic stress